

Supplementary Table 3. Testing the assumption of normality for Age and PET SUV variables in groups of patients with archival samples and patients with freshly collected samples.

Variable	Patients with archival samples	Patients with freshly collected samples
Age	$N=20, SW=0.89, p=0.03$	$N=20, S-W=0.97, p=0.68$
PET SUVmax	-	* $N=9$

PET – positron emission tomography; **SUVmax** – maximum standardized uptake value, N – number of observations (* N is small. The test has too little power to assess the difference of the distribution with the normal distribution. We assume that the distribution is statistically significantly different from the normal distribution); **S-W** - value of the Shapiro-Wilk test statistic; p – 1 level of statistical significance